

Rainwater Potabilization System: a PBL Experience for the Construction of Approached Technologies

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Abstract

This document describes the successful experience of a rainwater potabilization system developed within the framework of the PEAMA Sumapaz program of the Universidad Nacional de Colombia, in Bogotá. This system was developed at the Colegio Nuevo Horizonte sede D Torca, located in the rural area of Usaquén, Bogotá, through the practical application of concepts such as approached technologies, social appropriation of technology, socio-technical adequacy, Humanitarian Engineering and Engaged Engineering, through the methodology of Problem and Project Based Learning. This project was carried out during the second semester of 2022 and the whole 2023, in an interdisciplinary way, with the participation of students of economics, mechatronic engineering, mechanical engineering, civil engineering and agronomic engineering, who put into practice the knowledge acquired in the subjects they were taking at that time, and with the support of experts in the corresponding topics. The rainwater potabilization system was installed in the school, meets the physicochemical and microbiological parameters for human consumption and is functional, managed by students from the school and PEAMA Sumapaz, who were given the corresponding training. However, it continues to be improved and made more complex by the students who participated in its development, as well as by other PEAMA students and members of the school community.

Keywords: PBL; Humanitarian Engineering; low cost technologies; Engaged Engineering.

1 Introduction

This document gathers a successful PBL experience within PEAMA Sumapaz, from a critical point of view taking as a reference the concepts of humanitarian engineering and engaged engineering, and whose success is measured from the achievement of the social appropriation of the technology by the community involved.

The research was carried out in a multi-methodological way, through 1) the review of bibliography on the PEAMA Sumapaz, documents made by the students of the rainwater potabilization project, 2) the participant observation, since the authors have been an active part of the process and 3) semi-structured interviews made to members of the academic community of PEAMA Sumapaz, elaborated in the framework of Leonardo León's postdoctoral stay at the *Instituto De Estudios Ambientales of Universidad Nacional de Colombia*, whose research was entitled "PEAMA Sumapaz, a model of education for development?" and which also served as a background and basis for the present work, since it analyzes how students learn in the program through the PBL methodology.

This paper is divided into eight sections. First, we describe the context of PEAMA Sumapaz and nodo Torca. Then, we present the PBL Methodology used in this program. Next section presents the conceptual framework of this research composed by the concepts of Engaged Engineering and Humanitarian Engineering. This is followed by a description of the rainwater purification system, as well as the process of social appropriation of this technology by the community. Finally, learning outcomes, future work, and research conclusions are presented.

2 Context of Peama Sumapaz and nodo Torca

Based on the results of interviews with members of the Sumapaz community, students of the program and one of the creators of PEAMA Sumapaz, this program is the result of peasant struggles in the Bogotá town of Sumapaz, a territory hit by social and armed conflict, and with a high degree of social organization. This population had requested for years the presence of public education in the territory, with a contextualized model, since the majority of young people in the town could not access higher education and those who managed to do so were due to a great effort by their families, and at the cost of a process of depeasantization that forced young people to leave their territories and lose many of their customs in that transit. This contributes to the exodus and, therefore, to the lack of generational change in field work. Furthermore, the only job offer for professionals that continues to exist in the territory is as officials or contractors in institutions, without a peasant focus.

In this sense, PEAMA Sumapaz It is a special admission program, which began in 2016, as an accord between *Universidad Nacional de Colombia* and Bogotá city hall. It seeks to open university access to high school graduates who normally would not have it due to lack of resources and low admission scores. Under this program, students stay in the node for 4 semesters before going to the Bogotá campus (Gaitán-Albarracín, 2018; Cita Triana et al, 2020). Currently, the program has 3 nodes of action: *Nazareth*, *Torca* and *Ciudad Bolívar*. In each of the nodes, classes have a Project-Based Learning approach, whereby in each semester an integrative project is carried out in interdisciplinary groups (Rodríguez-Mesa, 2023).

Torca is a rural zone in the north of Bogotá. In this site, it is *Nuevo Horizonte* School, a public institution where one of the nodes of PEAMA Sumapaz take place. This node is for students who graduated from a rural school in the localities of *Suba*, *Usaquén*, *Chapinero* and *Santa Fe*. It is close to a forest reserve, and it does not have access to potable water.

3 PBL Methodology in PEAMA Sumapaz

The quest for authenticity in learning, brings about the need to align educational experiences with real-world STEM (Nicholas & Scribner, 2021; Ochoa-Duarte, León Rojas & Reina-Rozo, 2021). In addition, PBL is an effective teaching and learning strategy, as it allows for longer retention of learned concepts, improves problem-solving skills and enhances critical thinking, and has shown good results for rural education (Osman & Krieg, 2021). Moreover, the lack of access of rural students to high quality educational resources causes a delay in academic performance and a deficiency in competencies (Cheng, & Carolyn Yang, 2023), which processes such as PEAMA Sumapaz seek to diminish.

Thus, PEAMA Sumapaz has been built from the framework of constructivist education, particularly from the Project-Based Learning methodology. Under this model, students must develop a project in interdisciplinary groups, throughout the academic semester, framed in the subjects they are taking and based on a problem from a community, hopefully from the rural areas of Bogotá and related to the PEAMA environment.

3.1 Description of PEAMA Sumapaz model

Those who enter PEAMA Sumapaz must go through an academic process in three phases. In the first, students take the subjects under the Project Based Learning (PBL) methodology in the territory, for three or four semesters, depending on the degree. In the second phase, students do academic mobility to the Bogotá campus, where they study the other subjects. In the final phase, the degree work must be done returning to the rural communities of Bogotá, so that there is a greater probability of remaining in their place of origin after graduation and there is a return to the territory.

According to the relevant actors in the creation of the program, the main objective of PEAMA Sumapaz is to provide a differential and consistent mechanism of access and permanence in the institutional, economic, pedagogical and psychosocial aspects to young people from the rural areas of Bogotá to Universidad Nacional de Colombia, taking into account the low educational offer that exists in those areas, so that knowledge relevant to their contexts is built, contributing to local development, contributing to the care of the ecosystem and strengthening the relationship between the academy and the communities, through the Project Based Learning methodology.

From a pedagogical point of view, there has been an effort to break with banking education, betting on a constructivist model through the PBL methodology, since the concept is rooted in experiential experience, as opposed to the behavioral tradition. Hence, great importance is given to the development of skills considered vital such as learning to read, observe, construct questions, propose hypotheses (Gaitán-Albarracín, 2018), as well as work as a team and reach collective consensus. , since these are fundamental for an active teaching-learning process that enhances creativity.

The hegemonic academy, framed in the coloniality of knowledge, has not only excluded different knowledge but also the subjects who carry it, thus discriminating against popular knowledge (Guido-Guevara & Soler-Martín, 2023). In the case of PEAMA Sumapaz, the intention is to put the knowledge of the communities in dialogue with academic knowledge during the development of the projects. However, there is a permanent tension here, since it does not always occur, since it depends on many factors, such as the abilities, interests and knowledge not only of the students but also of the teachers who guide them in the learning process, as well as of the intended or actually achieved scope of the projects and whether they continue or not.

4 Engaged Engineering and Humanitarian Engineering in praxis

This section shows the concepts of engaged engineering and humanitarian engineering, which have been worked on by the authors of this paper and which serve as a framework for the analysis of the experience of the rainwater potabilization system project.

Engaged Engineering is a broad concept aimed at encompassing engineering practices that transcend the ethical boundaries of traditional engineering, fostering a more inclusive relationship among science, technology, and society (Ochoa-Duarte & Reina-Rozo, 2022). This approach strives to incorporate a range of practices and methodologies that benefit diverse populations. It involves initiatives within engineering institutions, inclusive development actions, the establishment of new educational guidelines, collaborative efforts with marginalized communities, non-profit organizations, social enterprises, and social technology networks, among others (Kleba, 2017; Ochoa-Duarte & Reina-Rozo, 2022).

Therefore, the concept of Engaged Engineering embraces diversity by integrating various approaches and a wide array of practices, methodologies, and perspectives aimed at advancing science and technology for the betterment of society, aligning closely with the Engaged STS program (Sismondo, 2008). In doing so, it seeks to surpass the ethical limitations of traditional engineering and reframe the relationships between engineering, nature, and society over time (Catalano, 2006).

Under the umbrella of Engaged Engineering, we find Humanitarian Engineering, which can be defined as the convergence of community knowledge, human sciences, science and technology in engineering praxis. Through the co-creation of teaching, reflection, research, innovation and manufacturing processes, the empowerment and technological appropriation of communities is strengthened. This allows the generation of solutions to circumstances that put marginalized populations at risk or in a state of vulnerability, in a way that

promotes good living within the community, understood as harmony in the relationship with others, with nature, and with himself, through ethical action (León Rojas, 2020).

Humanitarian engineering and engaged engineering, in praxis, correspond in this context to how, from teaching practice, students design and execute high-impact projects in their communities, while learning their disciplines. This is a constructivist approach, in which it is conceived that knowledge is not given but is constructed during the pedagogical process, generating appropriation of science and technology by students and other members of the communities in a way active, while contributing to the solution of real problems (Ochoa-Duarte, León Rojas y Reina-Rozo, 2021).

Project-based learning allows the development of these two concepts in depth, since the students learn by doing. Also, this methodology leaves the epistemological framework of Western science, and values other experiences and knowledge. In addition, the most important thing is that the pedagogical process does not remain in a simple characterization of the problems, but goes beyond, designing and building technological solutions, both appropriate and low cost, benefiting a community, including it in the different phases of the projects and not in an instrumental way (Cruz, Ochoa-Duarte & León, 2023).

5 Description of the water potabilization project

This section presents the general description of the design and construction process of the rainwater potabilization system, through participant observation and documentation of the project done during three semesters by the PEAMA Sumapaz students involved.

Considering that the school's most important problem is the lack of access to drinking water, students from the *Torca* node proposed a rainwater purification system in the second semester of 2022. From that academic period until the second semester of 2023, this group of students designed, manufactured, assembled, tested, implemented and improved the rainwater purification system.

In 2022-2, the group consisted of six students who were in their second semester in agronomy engineering, civil engineering, mechanical engineering, mechatronics engineering and economics. During this period, they designed and executed a pilot plan, using the infrastructure of a room designed to collect rainwater, as shown in figure 1. The result was poor, because it did not meet expectations and because they did not consider a process of social appropriation of the technology. However, the group committed itself to solve all the drawbacks, both internal and external, that did not allow a functional system. This decision was fundamental for the future success of the project, since it is common that every time an academic period is completed, a new project is started the next one, especially when the results were not successful.

Figure 1. First potabilization system

Thus it was that in 2023-1, the same group of students resumed the project, improving the prototype built previously, leaving it functional, although the physicochemical and microbiological properties did not fully comply with the parameters established for the water to be drinkable. This time workshops were held with school students and an operating manual was made, although with errors, in pursuit of social appropriation of the technological system, as shown in figure 2. Although there was significant progress compared to the previous semester, it was still not ready for use and there was a latent danger that all the accumulated work would be lost, since there was already pressure from PEAMA Sumapaz teachers to show concrete results or start a new project.

So, in 2023-2, the group decided to fulfill the commitments made to the school community and as an act of dignity, they insisted on continuing and finishing what they had proposed. This time they had two fewer members because one of them made the transition to the main campus of the university and the other was expelled from the university due to poor academic performance. In addition, the fact that three students in the group enrolled in the Electronics Workshop course played in their favor, since it allowed them to explore new perspectives and devices to implement in the water treatment system and because it made them take more interest in mechanical engineering and mechatronics engineering careers. In this period the progress was more significant, there was joint work with school students, a management plan was delivered and the system was functional. Besides, this project was presented at the *IV Encuentro Colombiano de Ingeniería y Desarrollo Social (ECIDS)* in Pereira (Polania & Quiroga, 2023).

Figure 2. Second potabilization system and workshop with the community

Although the idea was that from 2024-1 the purification system would be solely in charge of the school community, it was fortunate that first semester students decided to do a project based on the installed device, adding a centrifugation system of filtered water to avoid colony-forming units, taking into account that there is now an industrial design career at PEAMA Sumapaz.

6 Social appropriation of the potabilization system

Social appropriation of technology is a process in which citizens and communities use technological tools consciously and intentionally, recognizing their usefulness for educational, labor and social development. This process involves an active and participatory interaction with technology, where users not only adopt and use it, but also explore, evaluate and adjust it to meet their specific needs. It is a dynamic process that goes beyond simple adoption, generating changes in both user practices and in the technology itself (Lozano Borda & Pérez-Bustos, 2012). In the digital era, especially during situations such as the pandemic, the social appropriation of technology becomes fundamental, given the crucial role played by information and communication technologies in educational and work environments (Dávila-Rodríguez, 2020).

Figure 3. Tank truck that supplies the school

The project had an important component of social appropriation of technology that, although late, was successful in two ways. On the one hand, towards the school community, by making it part of the process and, on the other, within the PEAMA Sumapaz community, which is something little addressed when talking about social appropriation. To achieve this, we started from a deep understanding of the concepts of appropriate technologies and low-cost technologies, which imply knowledge of the territory, contextual design and use of environmental resources.

The first thing is that the project arose from a problem at the school: the lack of access to drinking water. To solve this problem, several options have been sought, among which is the use of a tank truck (figure 3), which is the way in which the school has been supplied, but, due to poor management of the storage tanks, the water becomes contaminated sooner. to reach the taps. Furthermore, in this search for solutions, the last two rooms that were built were built with roofs designed to capture rainwater, which is why one of them was used for the purification system. The starting point was, then, an infrastructure already adequate for the system and a prioritization of the problem by the school community.

Then, with difficulties and delays, school students were incorporated into the process, so that they learned about the existence and operation of the water treatment system, through practical workshops and discussions within the framework of the event "Art and Rurality" that takes place every year at the institution. Thus, tenth grade young people were empowered to take charge of maintaining the system, while several children, little by little, began to trust the device, so that they now drink water from it, as shown in figure 4.

Figure 4. Children using the potabilization system

The relationship between PEAMA Sumapaz students and the school community grew closer thanks to the rainwater purification system, which facilitated the joint realization of other projects such as hydroponic cultivation in the school greenhouse, which has been developing horizontally between the different actors that converge in the territory.

On the other hand, despite several setbacks at the beginning of the project, the students in the group increasingly took ownership of the purification system. At first, they saw it as a simple requirement to be able to take the subjects in a manner consistent with the PBL, so they did it in an undisciplined manner, without independent work and dependent on the PEAMA Sumapaz tutors. However, as the results were obtained, it became a personal and collective challenge for the members of the group, of which they are proud, to the point of taking it to the IV Colombian Meeting of Engineering and Social Development (ECIDS in Spanish) in Pereira in 2023. In addition, managed to convince several students who recently entered PEAMA Sumapaz in 2024-1 to continue improving the system.

Finally, what we consider most important in terms of the social appropriation of technology is the fact that two students in the group have continued working on the purification system, no longer to solve the specific problem of the Nuevo Horizonte School, but to achieve scale it, so that it can be implemented in other places in the country with the same problems and similar conditions. This is summarized by Figure 5.

Figure 5. Final potabilization system and workgroup

7 Learning outcomes and future work

The interdisciplinary approach used in this project not only allowed students to acquire technical knowledge, but also skills in teamwork, effective communication and complex problem solving in a real-world environment. By forming groups of students from different fields, participants were able to integrate diverse perspectives and approaches, thus enriching their solutions and fostering creativity and innovation. This type of experience

not only gives them a broader view of engineering, but also prepares them to face real-world challenges that require holistic and collaborative solutions.

The social innovation promoted through this project highlights the importance of not only developing effective technologies, but also ensuring their positive impact and long-term sustainability in communities. Students learned to consider ethical, cultural and environmental aspects in their designs, prioritizing the well-being of people and the environment. This social and environmental awareness enables them not only to become competent engineers, but also agents of change committed to Buen Vivir of the communities, understood as the construction of harmony with nature, other human beings and ourselves (Hidalgo-Capitán et al., 2019). In this way, engineering education is transformed and dialogues with concepts such as Engaged Engineering, in order to contribute to the transition towards Buen Vivir (Ochoa-Duarte, 2024).

On the other hand, students were able to learn disciplinary concepts of engineering and economics, such as electronic circuits, physical infrastructure, machine design, technical drawing, cost analysis, computer programming, economic engineering, irrigation systems, among others. All this within a real context, in a much more enriching way than the abstract learning that takes place in a classroom on campus.

So, the lessons learned by the students who participated in the project include the experience of participating in a fully contextualized engineering project, in which through Engaged Engineering and Humanitarian Engineering, and by doing interdisciplinary work, a dialogue of knowledge is established to allow transforming realities. In this way, they learn about the importance of breaking with the conventional way of doing engineering, in which the community is seen as a user and nature is taken as a resource. Thus, through this experience, the students learn much more than the contents of the subjects, but rather they orient their work as students and future professionals in a field that seeks to confront the civilization crisis in which we currently live.

The future work is mainly from students who participated in the rainwater potabilization project, because they want to develop a potabilization system for other communities with the same problem. To achieve this, it is important that they continue working autonomously, in an interdisciplinary manner and incorporating the dialogue of knowledge, in order to continue favoring the social appropriation of technology. This is of great importance because the geographical, ecological, social and cultural diversity of the country means that each co-design and co-creation process must be adapted to its own context.

8 Conclusions

PEAMA Sumapaz program presents an innovative educational proposal that seeks to promote access and permanence of young people from rural areas of Bogotá at the Universidad Nacional de Colombia, through a pedagogical approach based on Project Based Learning (PBL). This approach, focused on the construction of knowledge relevant to local contexts, contributes to the Buen Vivir of communities, the care of the ecosystem and the strengthening of the relationship between academia and communities. The importance of this program is highlighted in breaking with traditional banking education, betting on a constructivist model that fosters essential skills such as observation skills, question formulation, hypothesis proposal, teamwork and collective consensus, fundamental elements for an active teaching-learning process that enhances creativity and critical thinking.

Despite the challenges inherent to the integration of popular and academic knowledge, PEAMA Sumapaz program represents a significant effort to bring this knowledge into dialogue during the development of the projects. However, a constant tension is evident due to various factors such as the skills, interests and knowledge of students and teachers, as well as the actual scope of the projects. In spite of these difficulties,

the program demonstrates a commitment to the inclusion of diverse knowledge and the promotion of meaningful learning that transcends the traditional boundaries of education, contributing to the integral formation of students and strengthening the relationship between academia and local communities.

Regarding the projects carried out in PEAMA Sumapaz, first of all, the importance of adopting an interdisciplinary and collaborative approach to solve complex problems is highlighted, recognizing the diversity of perspectives and knowledge as a fundamental asset for innovation and effectiveness of the proposed solutions. In addition, the need to transcend the conventional vision of engineering, integrating social, environmental and ethical aspects in the development of technologies that have a positive impact on communities is evident.

Finally, the importance of promoting the social appropriation of technology through the dialogue of knowledge and co-creation with local communities is highlighted, ensuring the relevance and sustainability of the implemented solutions. This approach not only strengthens the relationship between engineering and society, but also empowers students as agents of change capable of addressing current challenges from a comprehensive and committed perspective.

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